

Interference Mitigation in mm-Wave Backhaul Networks with Limited Channel-State Information

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Abstract—Our goal is to identify if limited channel-state information is sufficient in order to mitigate interferences between the stations of a wireless mobile backhaul network, which is especially of great importance if the network employs full-duplex operation or terrestrial and satellite links sharing the same spectrum. We analyze and compare the signal-to-interference-and-noise ratio of plain beam steering and zero-forcing beam steering for a millimeter-wave backhaul network with limited channel-state information where only the positions of the stations are known, while buildings and other possible sources of multi-path components are unknown. Numerical analyses based on raytracing in a realistic urban scenario reveal that zero-forcing beam steering outperforms plain beam steering by about 12 dB. Furthermore, we compare the steering approaches to block diagonalization with full channel-state information as a reference. For low noise situations as in wide-band communications, zero-forcing beam steering can achieve a similar signal-to-noise-and-interference ratio to block diagonalization. We conclude that knowing the positions of wireless backhaul stations obviates the need for expensive channel estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile communication faces the trend of an increasing number of users (internet of things) and larger amounts of data (high-definition multimedia content). Traffic forecasts [1] report that in urban areas 750 Gbps downlink and 125 Gbps uplink shall be available per square kilometer. As a consequence, service providers will employ denser networks of base stations that form smaller cells. Wired connections to all these base stations would result in high setup costs. This leads to the demand for wireless backhaul networks with high capacity and reconfigurability. The antenna arrays of the backhaul stations will be located above the roof tops with line of sight between them and use millimeter waves, e.g. at 28 GHz [2], to fulfill the bandwidth requirements.

Millimeter wave backhaul networks are somehow similar to today widely-employed fixed-link radio relay stations, that use high-gain directional antennas. However, fixed-link antennas do not fulfill all requirements of future backhaul networks. They especially cannot generate more than one beam simultaneously, i.e. transmit different signals to more than one station. Beams are usually aligned mechanically which makes them inflexible, and they do not come with integrated interference mitigation techniques, which might be essential for dense urban environments.

Although millimeter waves show higher pathloss compared to microwaves, they may form a symbiotic relationship

with emerging massive-MIMO technologies. Millimeter-wave massive-MIMO arrays can create high-gain beams to compensate the pathloss while their physical dimensions are still reasonable. Another and probably the most important feature of massive-MIMO beamforming is the possibility to mitigate interferences between the users of the same time and frequency resources. Interference mitigation is an important enabler for other advances in technologies towards higher data rates, e.g. full-duplex radio transmission [3] or spectrum sharing between terrestrial or satellite segments [4]. Therefore, beamforming for millimeter wave is presently a popular research topic. A good overview of the state of the art can be found in [5]. Most beamforming algorithms require channel-state information to cancel the interferences [6]. To measure and to feedback the channel, however, ties up radio resources, which makes channel estimation expensive for large antenna arrays [7].

In this paper we analyze and compare three linear beamforming algorithms in a realistic urban scenario based on raytracing. We evaluate the signal, interference, and noise power at two receiver stations supplied with different signals from a common transmitter station. All three stations are equipped with stacked uniform circular arrays [8] of the same size. The first and second algorithm, plain beam steering and zero-forcing beam steering [9], rely on limited channel knowledge while the third algorithm, block diagonalization [10], requires full channel-state information. We investigate the influence of direct (line-of-sight) and multi-path (non-line-of-sight) interferences in order to assess the importance of channel-state information for a wireless backhaul network in a realistic urban scenario.

Notation: We use italic letters for scalars, lower-case bold-face letters for column vectors, and upper-case bold-face letters for matrices. The superscripts T , H , and $^{-1}$ denote the transposition, conjugate transposition, and matrix inversion, respectively. The Frobenius norm of a matrix is referred to as $\|\cdot\|_F$. Furthermore, \mathbf{I}_N denotes the identity matrix of size N , and $\mathbf{0}_{M \times N}$ is the zero matrix of size $M \times N$.

II. LINK BUDGET AND SCENARIO

We consider the requirements for a wireless backhaul network that have been derived in the Horizon 2020 project SANSA [11]. The link distance between two backhaul stations in an urban scenario is assumed to be between 200 m and 1400 m. In order to achieve a bit-error ratio of at least 10^{-4}

Fig. 1. Line-of-sight (red) and non-line-of-sight region (blue) within the scenario, evaluated at a height of 27 m above the ground.

with 1024-QAM, a signal-to-noise ratio of 36 dB must be ensured. (The influence of interferences has not been considered in [11].) Assuming a receiver noise power of -90 dBm, which is an optimistic estimate, an antenna gain of about 31 dBi is required at both ends of the link. In order to achieve such a high gain, a stacked uniform circular array of at least 1380 antennas (12 rings of 115 elements) must be employed [9].

Such a 1380-element antenna array has been considered for three wireless backhaul stations, one transmitter and two receivers, in the scenario shown in Fig. 1. The upper green circle indicates the position of the transmitter station. It is located on top of a building with an antenna height of 55 m. The red and blue areas depict the line-of-sight and non-line-of-sight regions, respectively. The position of the first receiver station is indicated by the lower green circle with an antenna height of 27 m, which is in the line-of-sight region of the transmitter.

The location of the second receiver is not fixed to a particular position, only its antenna height is set to 27 m, too. In the following analyses, the position of the second receiver station will be varied over the whole map in order to generate statistical data.

III. MATHEMATICAL DESCRIPTION

A. Data model

We define the number of antennas at each backhaul station to be $N = 1380$ and the number of receiver stations to be $K = 2$. The transmitter excites its antenna array with the vector $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{W}_{\text{TX}}\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, where $\mathbf{W}_{\text{TX}} = [\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},1}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},K}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$ is the coefficient matrix of the precoding beamformer and $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ is the data symbol vector with s_k being the symbol for the k -th receiver and $\mathbb{E}\{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^H\} = \mathbf{I}_K$. The k -th column of \mathbf{W}_{TX} , $\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, denotes the beamforming vector for the k -th receiver. In addition, the power constraint $\|\mathbf{W}_{\text{TX}}\|_F^2 = P_{\text{TX}}$ is enforced, where P_{TX} is the total transmit power.

Adopting a narrow-band block-fading channel model, the received signal at the k -th receiver station's antenna ports is given by

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}_k, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the channel matrix between the transmitter and the k -th receiver station and $\mathbf{n}_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, P_n)$ is the i.i.d. additive white Gaussian noise with a noise power of P_n .

At the k -th receiver station, the beamformer $\mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ combines the signals at the antenna outputs to

$$\hat{s}_k = \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{W}_{\text{TX}} \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}^H \mathbf{n}_k \quad (2)$$

$$= \hat{s}_{s,k} + \hat{s}_{i,k} + \hat{s}_{n,k}, \quad (3)$$

which consists of the desired signal

$$\hat{s}_{s,k} = \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}^H \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} s_k, \quad (4)$$

the unintended interferences

$$\hat{s}_{i,k} = \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}^H \mathbf{H}_k \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq k}}^K \mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},i} s_i, \quad (5)$$

and the combined noise

$$\hat{s}_{n,k} = \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}^H \mathbf{n}_k. \quad (6)$$

Based on (4)-(6), we define the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), the signal-to-interference ratio (SIR), and the signal-to-interference-and-noise ratio (SINR) at the k -th receiver station as

$$\eta_{\text{SNR},k} = |\hat{s}_{s,k}|^2 / |\hat{s}_{n,k}|^2, \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{\text{SIR},k} = |\hat{s}_{s,k}|^2 / |\hat{s}_{i,k}|^2, \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{\text{SINR},k} = |\hat{s}_{s,k}|^2 / (|\hat{s}_{i,k}|^2 + |\hat{s}_{n,k}|^2), \quad (9)$$

respectively. The terms *minimum* SNR, SIR, and SINR refer to the minimum of these ratios across all receivers, i.e.

$$\eta_{\min} = \min \{ \eta_k \mid k = 1, \dots, K \}. \quad (10)$$

B. Channel matrices

The channel matrices $\mathbf{H}_k, k = 1, \dots, K$ have been derived from the results of a raytracer. The number of paths R_k between the transmitter and the k -th receiver station depends on the scenario and has been limited to $R_k \leq 20$. Each path is described by the path weight $\gamma_{k,r} \in \mathbb{C}$, the direction of departure $\Omega_{\text{TX},k,r}$, and the direction of arrival $\Omega_{\text{RX},k,r}$ with $r = 1, \dots, R_k$ being the path number. Using this information, we build the channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ as

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \sum_{r=1}^{R_k} \gamma_{k,r} \mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},k}(\Omega_{\text{RX},k,r}) \mathbf{a}_{\text{TX}}^H(\Omega_{\text{TX},k,r}), \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{a}_{\text{TX}}(\Omega) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},k}(\Omega) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ are the steering vectors defined for a plane wave impinging from the direction Ω at the transmitter and k -th receiver, respectively.

C. Beamforming weights

In this subsection we derive precoders $\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k}$ and the combiners $\mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k}, k = 1, \dots, K$ for the three beamforming methods that are compared in the following analyses.

1) *PBS*: Plain beam steering (PBS) is also often referred to as phased-array or matched-filter approach. The beamforming weights are adjusted to steer the main beam in the direction of the shortest distance (SD) between two communicating stations, i.e.

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} = \mathbf{a}_{\text{TX}}(\Omega_{\text{TX},k}^{\text{SD}}), \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k} = \mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},k}(\Omega_{\text{RX},k}^{\text{SD}}). \quad (13)$$

If no line-of-sight between the stations exists, Ω^{SD} points through obstacles causing high losses. For PBS, each station requires only information about the geometrical position of the communication partner as well as its own location in order to calculate the directions.

2) *ZFBS*: Zero-forcing beam steering (ZFBS) steers a beam in the direction of the intended communication partner while placing nulls in the directions of the other stations [9]. The beamforming weights are derived by solving

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{TX}}^{\text{H}} \mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} = \mathbf{e}_k, \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{RX},k}^{\text{H}} \mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k} = \mathbf{e}_k \quad (15)$$

with $\mathbf{e}_k = [\mathbf{0}_{1 \times k-1}, 1, \mathbf{0}_{1 \times K-k}]^{\text{T}} \in \{0, 1\}^{K \times 1}$ being the k -th unit vector and

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{TX}} = [\mathbf{a}_{\text{TX}}(\Omega_{\text{TX},1}^{\text{SD}}), \dots, \mathbf{a}_{\text{TX}}(\Omega_{\text{TX},K}^{\text{SD}})], \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{RX},k} = [\mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},k}(\Omega_{\text{RX},k,1}^{\text{SD}}), \dots, \mathbf{a}_{\text{RX},k}(\Omega_{\text{RX},k,K}^{\text{SD}})] \quad (17)$$

being the steering matrices at the transmitter and the k -th receiver, respectively. The variable $\Omega_{\text{RX},i,j}^{\text{SD}}$ either stands for the SD direction from the i -th to the j -th receiver if $i \neq j$, or the SD direction from the i -th receiver to the transmitter if $i = j$. Solving (14) and (15) with the method of Lagrange multipliers finally leads to the beamforming weights

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{TX}} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{TX}}^{\text{H}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{TX}})^{-1} \mathbf{e}_k, \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{RX},k} (\mathbf{A}_{\text{RX},k}^{\text{H}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{RX},k})^{-1} \mathbf{e}_k. \quad (19)$$

Compared to BPS, ZFBS requires additional channel-state information, namely the geometrical position of all reachable stations. However, this is still predefined and static information in case of a backhaul network with fixed locations.

3) *BD*: Our reference beamformer incorporates the idea of decomposing the channel into K non-interfering sub-channels by utilizing block diagonalization (BD). The precoder for the k -th receiver uses the null space of the channel $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{(K-1)N \times N}$ to the other stations, which is

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k = [\mathbf{H}_1^{\text{T}}, \dots, \mathbf{H}_{k-1}^{\text{T}}, \mathbf{H}_{k+1}^{\text{T}}, \dots, \mathbf{H}_K^{\text{T}}]^{\text{T}} \quad (20)$$

with the rank

$$\tilde{h}_k = \text{rank} \left\{ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k \right\} = \min \left\{ \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq k}}^K R_i, N \right\}. \quad (21)$$

We apply singular value decomposition (SVD) to

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_k \tilde{\Sigma}_k \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\text{H}} = \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_k \tilde{\Sigma}_k \left[\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\parallel}, \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\perp} \right]^{\text{H}}, \quad (22)$$

to obtain $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\perp} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times (N - \tilde{h}_k)}$, that comprises the $N - \tilde{h}_k$ last right singular vectors that form an orthogonal basis for the null space of $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k$. Please note that $\tilde{h}_k < N$ must be assured for this approach, which holds for our backhaul scenario.

In order to find the best precoder-combiner pair for the k -th receiver within the nullspace of $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_k$, we apply SVD to

$$\mathbf{H}_k \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\perp} = \mathbf{U}_k \Sigma_k \mathbf{V}_k^{\text{H}}. \quad (23)$$

The first column of \mathbf{U}_k and \mathbf{V}_k are the left and right singular vectors $\mathbf{u}_{k,1} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{k,1} \in \mathbb{C}^{(N - \tilde{h}_k) \times 1}$ that belong to the largest singular value, which means they provides the best power transfer. Therefore, we define our reference beamformers as

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{TX},k} = \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_k^{\perp} \mathbf{v}_{k,1}, \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{RX},k} = \mathbf{u}_{k,1}. \quad (25)$$

From the above equations we see that BD requires full channel-state information. As a consequence, costly channel estimation and feedback would be needed to employ it in the backhaul network.

IV. NUMERICAL ANALYSES

Numerical analyses were performed in which the second receiver station has been located at 6612 different uniformly distributed positions over whole the map in Fig. 1, while the transmitter and the other receiver station were kept at the locations indicated by the circles. For each of these 6612 positions, we calculated the received signal and interference power at both receiver stations for all three beamforming algorithms. The noise power of the receivers was assumed to be $P_n = -90$ dBm, and the total transmit power was $P_{\text{TX}} = 30$ dBm. We set the frequency to 28 GHz and evaluated just the horizontal polarization, which shows lower reflection losses [12]. The antenna arrays were assembled with isotropic radiators.

A. Signal-to-noise ratio

The cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the minimum SNR for the line-of-sight regions (diamond markers in Fig. 2) confirms the assumptions made on the required antenna size in [9]. The 1380-element stacked uniform circular array achieves an SNR of about 36 dB. It is noteworthy that the SNR of PBS, ZFBS, and BD is almost equal although ZFBS placed additional nulls and BD distributes the signal power spatially to incorporate multipaths, which suffers from higher pathloss due to longer ranges and additional reflection losses. The upper bound of about 47 dB results from the maximum SNR that can be achieved at the first receiver due to its fixed distance to the transmitter.

B. Signal-to-interference ratio

As the next step we investigate the minimum SIR for the line-of-sight regions (square markers in Fig. 2). Here BD significantly outperforms the other two algorithms. In 99% of the cases, the SIR is better than 100 dB (not visible in Fig. 2), i.e. BD suppresses the interferences practically perfectly. The

Fig. 2. CDF of the minimum SNR, SIR, and SINR for all positions with line-of-sight conditions.

steering approaches, however, suffer from interferences. For PBS, in 98% of the cases the interference power is higher than the noise power, caused by direct (SD) and indirect (multi-path) interferences. In case of ZFBS this number reduces to about 90% because the direct interferences are mitigated. Due to the same reason, ZFBS shows an about 12 dB higher SIR than PBS, which means ZFBS reduces the inference power by more than factor 10.

C. Signal-to-interference-and-noise ratio

Finally we investigate the minimum SINR in the line-of-sight regions (asterisk markers in Fig. 2). Bringing all effects together, we clearly see that the steering approaches, PBS and ZFBS, are interference-limited, while BD is limited by the receiver noise. ZFBS is approximately 12 dB ahead of PBS and at the same time about 12 dB behind BD. We conclude that multi-path (non-line-of-sight) interferences are still significant although the transmitted power is highly focused by the 1380-element antenna array. However, our initial assumption of -90 dBm noise power was quite optimistic, i.e. the receiver noise will surely be higher for wide-band systems. In such a case, the SINR of BD will reduce drastically but the performance of PBS and ZFBS will remain firm.

Increasing the noise power by about 12 dB leads to similar SINR performances of ZFBS and BD. In this case, the SNR and SIR curves of ZFBS will lie close to each other leading to a balanced SINR, which we consider as the optimal case in terms of energy and ressources. If, on the one hand, the SINR is noise-limited, too many ressources are spend to needlessly suppress the interferences, which is of course sub-optimal. And if, on the other hand, the SINR is interference-limited, too many ressources are spend to reduce the noise, i.e. to achieve a low noise figure in the receivers, which is sub-optimal too.

The spatial distribution of the minimum SINR in our scenario is depicted in Fig. 3. The dark blue areas are the highly-shadowed non-line-of-sight regions caused by the gray-

(a) PBS

(b) ZFBS

(c) BD

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of the minimum SINR. The red and the black circle indicate the position of the transmitter and the fixed receiver, respectively.

colored buildings. The noticeable radial lines in Fig. 3 (a) and (b) reflect the radiation pattern of the antenna arrays. The noticeable lines in Fig. 3 (c), e.g. the lighter line from $x \approx 700$ m, $y \approx 500$ m to $x \approx 1200$ m, $y \approx 400$ m, indicate positions with strong multi-path reflections.

Fig. 4. Beam patterns at the transmitter for $k = 2$ using (a) PBS, (b) ZFBS, and (c) BD. The second receiver (RX2) was located in the line-of-sight region at the coordinates $x = 905$ m and $y = 705$ m.

D. Array responses

Fig. 4 shows the beam patterns at the transmitter towards the second receiver ($k = 2$) located at the coordinates $x = 905$ m and $y = 705$ m. All three beamforming methods clearly form a main lobe in the direction of the second receiver. For the PBS beamformer, the first receiver (RX1) accidentally lies on side lobe leading to large interferences. The ZFBS beamformer steers a null towards the RX1, while showing an almost equal pattern to PBS. In case of the BD, again a null is placed towards RX1 as well as additional nulls in the proximity. They cause the cancellation of the remaining multipaths interferences.

As another results of our analyses we conclude that the initially intended 1024-QAM will obtain a higher bit-error rate due to the multi-path interferences. This leads to the implication that they must be taken into account during the link budget analysis, especially if the receivers are not noise limited, i.e. for small and medium bandwidths.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We showed that for realistic assumptions on transmit power, receiver noise power, and number of antenna elements in an urban environment, ZFBS is an effective method to suppress interferences while requiring just limited channel-state information. Since only the position of the other stations must be known, there is no need to spend radio resources for channel estimation and feedback in an urban wireless backhaul scenario. ZFBS shows about 12 dB higher SINR compared to PBS, and it achieves comparable results to BD in wide-band systems with large receiver noise.

We also pointed out that multi-path (non-line-of-sight) interferences are still significant in low-noise scenarios, although large antenna array were used. They show approximately 12 dB less power compared to the line-of-sight interferences, and therefore should be considered in the link-budget analysis.

Future refinements of our analyses will include implementation effects like quantization of the beamforming weights, hybrid digital/analog approaches, and wide-band beamforming as well as deploying both polarizations [13].

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